

INVESTIGATION OF VISCOELASTICITY AND CURE SHRINKAGE IN AN EPOXY RESIN DURING PROCESSING

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1. Introduction

Process-induced deformation in composite parts affects their qualities and demands a lot of efforts for the compensation.

Many researchers have developed process modeling or simulation tools for predicting the deformation [1-3]. They are effective for cost and time saving in the development of composite parts. It is, however, difficult to establish the accurate modeling due to the complexity of the input parameters, especially changing material properties during cure processing. Cure shrinkage and changing elastic state of a matrix resin during processing are well known parameters having an impact on the result of process modeling.

In this work, investigation of the cure shrinkage and viscoelasticity of an epoxy resin has been carried out for upgrading the prediction methods of process-induced deformation on composite parts.

2 Experiments

2.1 Resin viscoelasticity

The viscoelastic properties of an epoxy resin in a CFRP, T800S/3900-2B, were measured with a rotational rheometer, Rheology Co. Ltd MR-300 Soliquidmeter, at three ramp rates in temperature within the practical range, as 0.5°C/min., 2.0°C/min. and 2.8°C/min. up to 180°C and holding the temperature until the viscosity developed to the apparatus's limit. Constant amplitude of 0.5° and frequency of 0.5Hz were used for all measurements. The measurements were conducted at least twice in the same condition due to confirm the reliability of the obtained data.

2.2 Cure shrinkage

The cure shrinkages of the resin were measured with a dilatometer, Shibayama Scientific Co. Ltd S701, at the completely same conditions in temperature that

of the rheometer due to correlate the viscoelastic properties.

3 Test Results and Discussion

3.1 Resin Viscoelasticity

Storage and loss stiffness data measured with the MR-300 are shown in Fig.1. The two measurement data for each temperature conditions were almost same. All the storage stiffness developed over 12MPa could not be measured due to the limit of the apparatus.

The storage and loss stiffness data were time and temperature dependant. The resin degree of cure was calculated using the cure kinetics investigated by Dykeman[4]. The stiffness vs. the degree of cure, α , curves at all test cases are almost same. An example of the results, at the ramp rate of 2.0°C/min., is shown in Fig.2. The gel point was determined as the storage stiffness exceeds the loss stiffness. The average gel point of the degree of cure for all test cases was 0.50 ($\alpha=0.50$) to be the gel point of this resin.

The linear plots of the same data in Fig.2 are shown in Fig.3 to investigate the development of the elastic modulus. After the gel point, the storage stiffness begins to rise, and shoots up from around $\alpha=0.76$ just before the loss stiffness begins to drop. Another test case, at the ramp rate of 0.5°C/min., also shows the similar curves as seen in Fig.3. The glass transition temperatures were also calculated and shown in Fig.3. Because a resin elastic modulus depends on the glass transition. The glass temperatures after $\alpha=0.76$ are almost same in these cases. It means that only the degree of cure affects the elastic modulus within the practical ramp rates and the hold temperature of 180°C.

As mentioned above, the final stiffness after vitrification could not be measured. And storage and

loss stiffness measured with a rotational rheometer generally depend on the measurement frequency. It is difficult to determine the elastic modulus quantitatively. But due to implement the elastic modulus in process simulation, the fitting curve of the storage stiffness after gelation described in equation (1) was calculated.

$$\begin{aligned} G'_r &= 0, & \alpha < \alpha_{gel} \\ G'_r &= A_1 \exp\{K_1(\alpha - \alpha_{gel})^n\}, & \alpha_{gel} \leq \alpha < \alpha_{vir} \\ G'_r &= A_2 \exp\{K_2(\alpha - \alpha_{vir})\}, & \alpha \geq \alpha_{vir} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Where, the A_1 , K_1 , n , A_2 and K_2 are constants and the α_{gel} and α_{vir} are degrees of cure at the gelation and vitrification.

Each parameters of the equation (1) were determined with a least-square method to the test data and shown in Table 1. The fitting curve is shown in Fig.4 and good agreement with the measurement data. The elastic moduli used in process simulation were obtained by multiplication of this stiffness tailored to the deformation of specimens by cure shrinkage shown in sub section 3.3.

3.2 Cure shrinkage

Changes of the specific volume during process at three temperature conditions are shown in Fig.5. For two measurements at each temperature conditions, the first runs showed always higher volume than the second runs. The causes of the differences were not ascertained completely. One of the speculations is the variety of each batch because different batches of the resin were used for first runs and second runs. Or the effects of deforming action for the test setup might be different between first runs and second runs.

Although the differences of the absolute volume, the timing of the peak volume and the amount of reduction from the peak volume were almost same at each conditions. In this work, the cure shrinkage, V_r , was obtained by subtracting the effect of thermal expansion from the measured specific volume.

The thermal expansion lines were set with the two volumes at 90°C and 110°C for the case of 0.5°C/min. and at 90°C and 150°C for the cases of 2.0°C/min. and 2.8°C/min..

The specific volume after subtracting the thermal expansion vs. the degree of cure curves show same shape as shown in Fig.6. Some researchers have reported that the specific volumes were linear [2, 5] or quadratic[6] to the degree of cure. But the curves in Fig.4 do not fit the reported equations and have an inflection point near the gel point ($\alpha_{gel}=0.50$). Based on the test results, the cure shrinkage equation is proposed with modification of the quadratic equation as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} V_r &= 0, & \alpha < \alpha_1 \\ V_r &= A\alpha_{s1} + (V_r^{gel} - A)\alpha_{s1}^2, & \alpha_1 \leq \alpha < \alpha_{gel} \\ V_r &= V_r^{gel} + B\alpha_{s2} + (V_r^{inf} - V_r^{gel} - B)\alpha_{s2}^2, & \alpha_{gel} \leq \alpha < \alpha_2 \\ V_r &= V_r^{inf}, & \alpha \geq \alpha_2 \\ \alpha_{s1} &= (\alpha - \alpha_1) / (\alpha_{gel} - \alpha_1) \\ \alpha_{s2} &= (\alpha - \alpha_{gel}) / (\alpha_2 - \alpha_{gel}). \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Where, the V_r^{gel} and V_r^{inf} are volumetric cure shrinkage at gel point and complete cured. The α_{s1} and α_{s2} are degrees of cure at that the shrinkage begins and stops. The A and B are nonlinear factors before and after gel point.

Each parameters of the equation (2) were determined with a least-square method to all the test data and shown in Table 2. The fitting curve using the parameters is also shown in Fig.6 and good agreement with the measurement data can be seen.

3.3 Determination of the elastic moduli

Heating tests of asymmetric lay-up plates were conducted for determination of resin cure-induced deflection[7]. The specimens, length of 150mm and 250mm, and lay-up of [0₄/90₄] and [0₈/90₈] were used. The width of specimens were one tenth of the length. The test setup are shown in Fig.7. The specimens were heated up from room temperature to near the cure temperature, 180°C in an environmental chamber and the deflections were measured by a scale at about every 20°C up.

A example of the test results is shown in Fig.8. The deflections at 180°C are calculated from linear extrapolation of the measured data. Table 3 shows the deflections of all specimens at room temperature and at 180°C.

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FE models of asymmetric plates shown in Fig.9(a) were fabricated and the cure shrinkage analyses using the material properties described in equation (3) and equation (4) were conducted and the deformation of analysis results had same shape as on of the test results as shown in Fig.9(b).

$$E_1 = E_1(180^\circ\text{C}), E_2 = E_3 = \gamma G'_r \quad (3)$$

$$\beta_1 = 0, \beta_2 = \beta_3 = \delta(1 - \sqrt[3]{1 - V_r}), \delta = 0.52 \quad (4)$$

Where the E_1, E_2 and E_3 are Young's moduli of fiber direction, transverse direction and through the thickness direction, respectively. And the γ is the multiplication factor. The β_1, β_2 and β_3 are cure shrinkage strains and δ is a fiber effect factor depending on the fiber volume fraction.

The deflections of FE analysis highly depended on the multiplication factor and shown in Fig.10. The multiplication factor of 33 was the best fit with the test results.

Other case's results of the FE analyses using $\gamma=33$ are shown in Table 4 and had good agreements with the test results.

4 Conclusions

Viscoelastic properties and resin cure shrinkages were investigated and could be aligned using the degree of cure based on the heat generation during resin curing.

The resin gel point was determined to be 0.5 in the degree of cure and the storage stiffness shoot up at 0.76 in the degree of cure.

Resin cure shrinkage equation is proposed based on the test results which have an inflection point near the gel point.

The elastic moduli during resin curing for process simulation are determined from multiplication of the storage stiffness to fit FE analysis with the asymmetric lay-up plate test results.

(a) Ramp rate of 0.5 °C/min.

(b) Ramp rate of 2.0 °C/min.

(c) Ramp rate of 2.8 °C/min.

Fig.1. Storage stiffness and loss stiffness measured with a MR-300

Fig.2. Viscoelastic stiffness vs. degree of cure (Ramp rate of 2.0°C/min.).

Fig.3. Viscoelastic stiffness and difference temperature from the glass transition vs. degree of cure (Ramp rates of 0.5°C/min. and 2.0°C/min.).

Fig.4 Fitting curve of the storage stiffness

(a) Ramp rate of 0.5 °C/min.

(b) Ramp rate of 2.0 °C/min.

(c) Ramp rate of 2.8 °C/min.

Fig.5. Changes of the specific volume measured with a S701

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Fig.6. Specific volume after compensation vs. degree of cure (all cases)

Fig.7. Photograph of the heating test of an asymmetric lay-up plate

Fig.8. Measured deflection on asymmetric lay-up plates (Length of 150mm and lay-up of $[0_4/90_4]$)

(a) FE mesh and the boundary conditions

(b) Deformation after cure shrinkage (10 times exaggerated)

Fig.9. FE model of the asymmetric plate (Length of 150mm and lay-up of $[0_4/90_4]$, $\gamma=33$)

Fig.10. Deflection after cure calculated by FE analyses with changing multiplication factors (Length of 150mm and lay-up of $[0_4/90_4]$)

Table 1 Fitting parameters of the equation (1)

A_1	A_2	K_1	K_2	n	α_{gel}	α_{vir}
182.6	3.88×10^6	14.44	35.65	0.271	0.50	0.76

Table 2 Fitting parameters of the equation (2)

α_{s1}	α_{s2}	α_{gel}	V_r^{gel}	V_r^{inf}	A	B
0.03	0.83	0.50	0.040	0.063	0.021	0.029

Table 3 Test summary of the heating tests of asymmetric lay-up plates

		Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4
Length [mm]		150		250	
Lay-up		[0 ₄ /90 ₄]	[0 ₈ /90 ₈]	[0 ₄ /90 ₄]	[0 ₈ /90 ₈]
Deflection at R.T. [mm]	1	7.8	3.8	19.3	10.8
	2	7.8	4.3	20.0	11.0
	3	8.0	4.0	20.0	11.0
	Ave.	7.8	4.0	19.8	10.9
Deflection at 180°C [mm]	1	0.6	0.0	0.7	1.0
	2	0.8	0.3	0.9	0.6
	3	0.2	0.4	1.9	0.7
	Ave.	0.5	0.2	1.2	0.8

Table 4 Comparison between the test results and FE results using the multiplication factor of 33

		Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4
Length [mm]		150		250	
Lay-up		[0 ₄ /90 ₄]	[0 ₈ /90 ₈]	[0 ₄ /90 ₄]	[0 ₈ /90 ₈]
Test result [mm]		0.5	0.2	1.2	0.8
FE result [mm]		0.5	0.3	1.4	0.7

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